

Effect of planting date on grain yield of cultivar Morelos A92 and breeding line CAEZ401. Zacatepec, Morelos, Mexico. 1993.

Filled grains panicle⁻¹ and grain weight were the most affected by late transplanting. For the two genotypes, filled grains panicle⁻¹ went down from 63 in the first date to 47 in the last date while 1,000 grain weight was reduced from 43.6 to 40.7 g.

The regression equations obtained and the parameters used to evaluate fitness of the models in each period are shown in the table. Within each period, the best fit was obtained when GR and MMT were

evaluated together (model 4), except in the period f+20, when MMT and MMT2 (model 2) were comparable. The fitness of model 4 was higher for f-20 and f+20 than their combination.

These results show that variation in incident global radiation and mean minimum temperature during the period 20 d before or 20 d after flowering may explain much of the variation in grain yield in the different planting dates for irrigated rice. ■

Integrated pest management—diseases

Effects of neem derivatives on sheath rot in scented rice

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We assessed the efficacy of botanical biocides and pesticides (fungicides carbendazim and mancozeb) for controlling sheath rot (ShR) of scented rice. Leaf extract and fungicides were applied twice as foliar sprays at a 2-wk interval beginning at booting. The field trial was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications using scented hybrid rice JJ92. Plot size was 5 × 2 m.

ShR incidence was measured as the percentage of infected tillers in 25

Comparison of biocides to control sheath rot incidence and grain yield of scented rice JJ92.

Treatment	Percent ShR incidence ^a	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)
Neem oil (3%)	30.22 (33.25)	5.2
Neem seed kernel extract (5%)	26.30 (29.70)	5.0
Monocrotophos (1250 ml ha ⁻¹)	25.86 (30.48)	4.4
Carbendazim (500 g ha ⁻¹)	24.27 (29.80)	4.1
Mancozeb (1 kg ha ⁻¹)	30.47 (33.38)	3.4
Monocrotophos (1250 ml) + carbendazim (500 g ha ⁻¹)	27.57 (31.61)	3.8
Monocrotophos (1250 ml) + mancozeb (1 kg ha ⁻¹)	22.87 (28.49)	4.5
Nochi (10%) (<i>Vitex negundo</i>)	26.80 (31.10)	4.2
Untreated check	37.52 (37.67)	3.2
LSD (P=0.05)	1.10	.5

^aMeans of three replications. Data in parentheses are arcsine-transformed values.

randomly selected hills/plot 20 d after the last spray. Higher yields were recorded with neem oil (3%), neem seed kernel extract (5%), and monocrotophos (1,250 ml ha⁻¹) + mancozeb (1 kg ha⁻¹). Standard fungicides carbendazim (500 g ha⁻¹) and monocrotophos (1,250 ml ha⁻¹), and

mancozeb (1 kg ha⁻¹) effectively reduced ShR incidence (see table).

Using a spray of neem seed kernel extract generated higher grain yield and effectively reduced disease incidence, although to a lesser degree, than using regular fungicides. ■

Seed borne nature and seed transmission of rice sheath blight

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Although rice sheath blight (ShB) caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* is documented as a seedborne disease, evidence of this nature is lacking. We investigated spotted and apparently healthy seeds of rice cultivar Swarna Mashuri to find out the mode of transmission involved. The seeds were collected from a heavily ShB-infected rice crop from the BCKV Regional Research Farm.

Effect of *R. solani* infection on rice germination and seed health. West Bengal^a, India.

Treatment	Seeds yielding <i>R. solani</i> (%)	Germination (%)	Seedling infection (%)	Seedling collapse (%)	Shoot fresh weight (mg)	Shoot dry weight (mg)	Root fresh weight (mg)	Root dry weight (mg)
Naturally Infested seeds	37.83	59.09	14.88	4.35	279.46	46.83	485.7	64.1
Artificially inoculated seeds	56.35	70.66	23.58	9.21	361.20	66.05	673.75	120.13
Apparently healthy seeds	12.17	73.19	0	0	467.26	94.3	922.4	174.3
SE ±	0.682	0.655	0.728	0.127	0.57	0.376	0.575	0.324
LSD (0.05)	1.520	1.459	1.624	0.284	1.286	0.838	1.281	0.721
Unsterilized seeds	50.92	65.63	8.70	9.09	334.66	60.52	608.66	109
Surface-sterilized seeds	19.98	69.67	6.93	0	403.94	77.60	779.23	130.02
SE ±	0.545	0.535	0.594	0.018	0.47	0.307	0.469	0.265
LSD (0.05)	1.214	1.19	1.326	0.024	1.050	0.684	1.04	0.590
Interaction								
SE ±	0.9315	0.9266	1.03	0.032	0.81	0.532	0.813	0.459
LSD (0.05)	2.07	2.06	2.29	0.072	1.819	1.85	1.81	1.022

^aAll percentage data are transformed angular values.